

Nucleophilicity of aromatic and aliphatic hydroxamate ions towards C=O and P=O center in cationic micellar media

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Abstract : The kinetics of the hydrolysis of *p*-nitrophenyl benzoate (PNPB) and *p*-nitrophenyldiphenyl phosphate (PNPDPP) by hydroxamate ions (R'(C=O)N(RO⁻)) have been investigated in aqueous cationic micellar media at pH 6.5 to 12.0 and 27 °C. The pseudo-first order rate constants-surfactant profiles show micelle assisted bimolecular reaction involving an interfacial exchange between bulk aqueous media and micellar pseudophase. All the hydroxamate ion shows higher reactivity in cationic micellar media. Pseudophase model has been applied in order to determine micellar second order rate constant and binding constant.

Keywords : α -Nucleophile, phosphate and carboxylate ester, cationic surfactant, pseudophase model.

Introduction

Organophosphate triesters, pesticides and insecticides are used for decades, and other toxic organophosphorus compounds are very lethal nerve agents. Many deaths occur in the young economically active age group due to this organophosphorus pesticides^{1,2}. Fatality in 20% of the intoxication cases are common and the World Health Organisation (WHO) has estimated that 200,000 people die each year because of pesticide poisoning³. Organophosphorus pesticide poisoning is a major health problem, a leading cause of death in the countries of South-East Asia region and a number of controversies exist on the effective treatment⁴. The toxicity of these compounds is due primarily to the practically irreversible inhibition of acetylcholinesterase (AChE), the enzyme responsible for hydrolysis of the neurotransmitter acetylcholine. The search for better antidotes is still based on the trial and error⁵. Due to their biological and environmental significance, their degradation has been extensively investigated using different hydrolyzing α -nucleophiles agent⁶⁻⁸.

Hydroxamate ions bear one or more nonbonding electron pairs at the position α - to the nucleophilic center have been termed α -nucleophiles and exhibit enhanced reactivity compared with normal nucleophiles of similar

basicity (the α -effect)⁹⁻¹¹. The effective deacylating and dephosphorylating properties of amphiphilic hydroxamate ions are increased by micellization with surfactant in water^{12,13}. It has been proved that hydroxamic acid behaves as a self-destructive intramolecular scissor, which reacts and loses nucleophilic ability after reaction¹⁴. In recent studies of the reactions of nucleophilic reagents with carboxylate and phosphate esters, a significant catalytic activity have been observed. Over the pH range 6.7-11.4, bifunctional nucleophilicity of hydroxamate ion have been documented^{15a,b}.

Current interest in studying the reaction of α -nucleophiles has received major new impetus from the importance of many applications of these highly reactive species¹⁶⁻²⁰. For example in the development of protocols for environmental decontamination of sites polluted with organophosphorus insecticides, α -nucleophiles such as oximates have been demonstrated to be highly effective²¹. The needs to develop efficient means to destroy stockpiles of organophosphorus nerve agents have led a number of groups to investigate different approaches toward enhancing decomposition of these agents; α -nucleophiles can accelerate these decontamination^{22,23}. No doubt the high reactivity of α -nucleophiles will also find uses in

synthetic organic chemistry. The nucleophiles exhibiting α -effect are oximate ($R_2C=NO^-$)²⁴, hydroxamate ($RC(O)NHO^-$)²⁵, peroxides (ROO^-)²⁶, hydroxylamine (NH_2OH)²⁷, hydrazine ($RNH-NH_2$)²⁸, hypochlorite^{29,30}, hydroxybenzotriazoles/tetrazoles³¹ and iodosylcarboxylates³² etc. *N*-Hydroxamides are structural analogues of hydroxamic acids with N-OH functional group. In the present investigation, we have studied the nucleophilic reactions of aceto-benzo and naphthohydroxamate ions with *p*-nitrophenyl benzoate and *p*-nitrophenyl diphenylphosphate in the absence and presence of cationic surfactants (Scheme 1). The effect of substitution on hydroxamate ion and head group of cationic surfactants have been discussed.

Scheme 1. Nucleophilic reaction of hydroxamate ions with *p*-nitrophenyl benzoate and *p*-nitrophenyl diphenyl phosphate.

Micellar rate effects have been quantitatively determined on the basis of pseudophase models that high local concentrations of nucleophiles are largely responsible for the rate acceleration in the interfacial micellar region³³⁻³⁶.

Experimental

Materials :

Hydroxylamine hydrochloride ($NH_2OH.HCl$), aceto-hydroxamic acid (AHA), benzohydroxamic acid (BHA), salicylhydroxamic acid (SHA), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and cetylpyridinium bromide (CPB) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich chemicals Pvt. Ltd., Bangalore (India). Naphthohydroxamic acid (NHA) was prepared by reaction of esters with hydroxylamine in alkaline condition³⁷. Water was purified with a Millipore Mili-Q-water system.

Methods :

Kinetic measurements :

The reactions were studied spectrophotometrically using Evolution 300 Thermoscientific UV-Visible spectrophotometer by monitoring the appearance of leaving *p*-nitrophenoxide ion at 400 nm and 27 ± 0.2 °C (Fig. 1). All kinetic experiments were performed at an ionic strength of 0.1 *M* (with KCl). Borate buffer was employed to control the pH of the reaction media. All the pH measurements were obtained using a Thermoscientific Orion Star A-211 pH-meter. All the reactions were conducted under pseudo-first order condition with the nucleophile in ex-

cess. For all the kinetic runs, the absorbance/time result fit very well to the following first order rate equation.

$$\ln(A_\infty - A_t) = \ln(A_\infty - A_0) - kt \quad (1)$$

The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) were determined from the plots of absorbance versus time with A_0 , A_t and A_∞ being the absorbance values at zero, time and infinite time, respectively. The substrate (PNPB, PNPDP) concentration was kept constant for all the reaction (1×10^{-4} *M*). Kinetic studies were performed at various concentration of cationic surfactant to investigate the effect of surfactant on the cleaving efficiency of hydroxamate ions.

Results and discussion

pH-Dependent reaction :

Pseudo-first order rate constant for the reaction of PNPB with benzohydroxamate (BHA^-) and

Fig. 1. Repeat scans spectra for the production of *p*-nitrophenoxide ion. Reaction condition : Temp. = 27 °C, [BHA⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, [PNPB] = 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, [KCl] = 0.1 M, pH = 9.2 (borate buffer).

naphthohydroxamate ion (NHA⁻) have been measured spectrophotometrically at 27 °C. The pH dependent rate constant (k_{obs}) increases with increasing pH in between the range 6.6–12.0. The kinetic curves plotted in Fig. 2 illustrate variation of k_{obs} at different pH for the reaction of 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M PNPB with 1.0 × 10⁻³ M HA. The rate of reaction shows drastic change at the 50% hydroxamic acid deprotonated, i.e. pK_a, of hydroxamic acid. The pK_a of hydroxamic acid was determined pH-metrically.

Fig. 2. Plots of first order rate constants vs pH for the reaction of PNPB with BHA⁻ and NHA⁻. Reaction condition : Temp. = 27 °C, [BHA⁻ and NHA⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, [PNPB] = 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, [KCl] = 0.1 M.

Hydroxamic acids have been suggested to behave either as NH or OH acids depending on solvent^{38,39}. Numerous studies indicate that hydroxamic acids are OH, rather than NH, acids in H₂O³⁸. It is the anion of hydroxamic acid (N-O⁻) acts as a reactive species in the hydrolysis of esters. Consequently, the pK_a for the conversion of the N-OH to N-O⁻ (Scheme 2) plays significant role for the hydrolysis of phosphate ester. The ionized species of hydroxamic acid, i.e. hydroxamate ions acts as true catalyst. At higher pH, the rate constants could not be measured, because the reaction is very fast. The ionized form

Scheme 2. Ionization of hydroxamic acid.

of hydroxamic acid (hydroxamate) is responsible for the enhanced rate of reaction for the cleavage of phosphate ester. The pH-rate profile for the reaction is shown in Table 1. We examined nucleophilic reactivity of BHA⁻ and NHA⁻ under standard conditions [PNPB] = 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, [Nu⁻] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, [KCl] = 0.01 M and varied pH range (6.6–12.0), BHA⁻ shows large reactivity in comparison to NHA⁻.

Table 1. Summarize of pH-dependent pseudo-first order rate constants for the reaction of hydroxamate ions with PNPB

pH	10 ⁴ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)	
	BHA	NHA
6.5	–	0.691
7.0	3.81	0.759
7.5	4.60	–
8.0	7.75	0.80
8.5	10.2	3.91
9.2	13.5	9.08
9.5	19.5	–
10.0	21.3	2.77
11.0	22.1	6.25
12.0	23.0	8.10

Nucleophile concentration dependent reaction :

Second order rate constants (k_2) for the reaction of PNPB with all the nucleophiles were determined (Table 2). To calculate the second order rate constants for the anionic form of the nucleophiles, plots of k_{obs} vs [Nu⁻] were constructed and the values obtained as intercept of the plot = k_0 and slope as second order rate constant (k_2). It can be seen that AHA⁻ is more reactive than other nucleophiles at 9.2 pH for attacking the carboxylate center of PNPB. Comparison of the reactivity of HA⁻ ions for the reaction of PNPB provides a reliable evidence for the large α -effect of HA⁻ ions. The difference in the reactivity of AHA⁻ towards PNPB compared with NH₂O⁻, BHA⁻ and NHA⁻ is measure of intrinsic difference in

Table 2. Second order rate constants for the reaction of nucleophiles with *p*-nitrophenyl benzoate (PNPB)

Nucleophiles	pK _a	k ₂ (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
NH ₂ O ⁻	13.5	0.114 ± 0.010
BHA ⁻	8.68	9.57 ± 0.01 × 10 ⁻⁴
NHA ⁻	8.93	1.95 ± 0.02 × 10 ⁻³
AHA ⁻	9.29	5.45 ± 0.015 × 10 ⁻³

reactivity of the nucleophiles. In general, AHA⁻ ions are more reactive than other hydroxamate ions. Corresponding second order rate constants of AHA⁻ is 2.80 and 5.70 fold greater than the NHA⁻ and BHA⁻ for the reaction of PNPB.

Fig. 3. shows the Brönsted-type plot describing the reactivity of HA⁻ with PNPB in aqueous media. Brönsted-type nucleophilicity plots (Fig. 3) reveal a clear tendency of reactivity of HA⁻ increases with increasing basicity. Nome *et al.*⁴⁰ described similar tendency to reaction of bis(2,4-dinitrophenyl)phosphate with hydrazine and hydrogen peroxide. Terrier *et al.*⁴¹ reported the strong tendency of oximate ion (Ox⁻) reactivity to level off at pK_a ≈ 9.0 for the reaction of Sarin (GB), Soman (GD) and diisopropylphosphonofluoridate (DFP) in aqueous solution. Ashani and Cohen investigated the decomposition of DFP by pyridinium and structurally related aldoximes and noted that there was change in reactivity with varying the Ox⁻ structures⁴². The analysis of data on the basis of second order rate constant and pK_a of HA⁻ ion leads to the straight line as shown in Fig. 3. The observation of linear Brönsted-type plot is attributed to the solvation of N-O⁻ group of hydroxamate ions and there must be desolvation prior to nucleophilic attack of these anionic nucleophiles which becomes more difficult with increasing basicity⁴³. The plot of k_2 with the pK_a of the moderately basic HA⁻s (pK_a < 9.20) gives a linear Brönsted-type plot with a slope $\beta_{\text{nuc}} = 0.4001$, which is relatively agreement with reported by Terrier and co-worker for

Fig. 3. Brönsted type plots for the reaction of PNPB with hydroxamate ions.

the reaction DFP with oximes. The β_{nuc} value is suggestive of the concerted bond formation between nucleophile and the C=O center in the transition state followed by departure of *p*-nitrophenoxide anion.

Dependence of k_{obs} on [surfactant] :

Rate constants go through a maximum (Figs. 4-7) with increasing surfactant concentration at constant hydroxamate ions and substrate concentration which is typical of micellar-assisted bimolecular reactions. These rate maxima are observed because of “dilution effects” brought about by increasing concentrations of cationic surfactant. Initially, an increase in the surfactant concentration generates more cationic micelles and increases the initial rate. As the number of micelles becomes large, virtually all the substrate gets associated to the micellar phase. Further addition of surfactant proliferates the number of micelles which simply take up the nucleophilic anions into the “Stern layer”, thereby deactivating them, since substrate in one micelle cannot react with nucleophile in another.

The rate-surfactant concentration profiles obtained with various surfactants/catalysts are characteristic of the micelle catalyzed reaction. The variation of rate constants below the critical micelle concentration (cmc) is difficult to quantify due to reactant induced micellization and interaction with non-micellized surfactants. According to Buncl *et al.*⁴⁴, the electrostatic attraction of the cationic head groups of the surfactants at the micelle surface to

Fig. 4. Simulated rate-surfactant profile for the reaction of PNPB with NHA in various concentration of CTAB at pH 9.2. Reaction condition : Temp. = 27 °C, [NHA] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, [PNPB] = 1.0×10^{-4} M, [KCl] = 0.1 M, pH = 9.2 (borate buffer).

Fig. 5. Simulated rate-surfactant profile for the reaction of PNPB with (■) NHA⁻, (●) BHA⁻ in CPB micellar media (The solid lines are the results of fitting eq. (3)). Reaction condition : [PNPB] = 1.0×10^{-4} M, [Nu⁻] = 1.0×10^{-3} M, [KCl] = 0.1 M, pH = 9.2 (borate buffer), Temp. = 27 °C.

the nucleophilic anion counter ions leads to augmentation of the local concentration of the nucleophile, whereas incorporation of the substrate in the micelle leads to a higher local concentration of the substrate. This enhanced concentration of the reactants accounts for the higher rate of reaction. Implicit in this explanation is the requirement that the reactive site of the esters be situated in close proximity to the nucleophile, that is, at the micelle-water interface, the Stern layer. The subsequent addition of the cationic surfactant after cmc caused a decrease in the reaction rate possibly due to the decrease in the catalyst/reagent concentration in the micellar pseudophase. The excess of unreactive counterions (X⁻) compete with hydroxamate ions for available sites in the Stern layer.

Application of pseudophase model (PPM) :

Rate effects on bimolecular reactions in association colloids are rationalized by the pseudophase model⁴⁵, in which the aggregates and bulk solvent, typically water, are regarded as distinct reaction regions. The overall reaction rate is the sum of the rate in each pseudophase and depends on the rate constants and reactant concentrations in each pseudophase⁴⁶.

Scheme 3 can be proposed for applying the PPM model. In this model, subscripts w and m signify aqueous and micellar pseudophases, respectively, and D_n represents the micellized surfactant, that is, $[D_n] = [D_T] - \text{cmc}$, where $[D_T]$ is the stoichiometric surfactant concentration and cmc the critical micellar concentration, ob-

Scheme 3

tained under the experimental conditions as the minimum surfactant concentration required to observe any kinetic effect. Scheme 3 considers the distribution of substrate between the aqueous and micellar pseudophases, $K_m^{\text{Substrate}}$. The binding constant of PNPDP and PNPB were previously determined experimentally⁴⁷ with the value $K_m^{\text{PNPDPP}} = 7000 \text{ M}^{-1}$, $K_m^{\text{PNPB}} = 610 \text{ M}^{-1}$. The distribution of nucleophile between both the aqueous and micellar pseudophase have been governed by their K_m^{Nu} value. The different reactivities in the aqueous and micellar pseudophases have been taken into account through the corresponding second order rate constants: k_2^w and k_2^m . The hydroxamate concentration in the micellar pseudophase has been defined as the local, molar concentration within the micelle pseudophase: $[HA]_T = [HA]_m / D_n \bar{V}$, where \bar{V} is the molar volume in $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ of the reaction region and $[D_n] \bar{V}$ denotes the micellar fractional volume in which the reaction occurs. We assume \bar{V} equal to the partial molar volume of the interfacial reaction region in the micellar pseudophase, determined by Bunton⁴⁸ as $0.14 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. Micellar binding of substrate, esters and Nu^- , is governed by hydrophobic interactions and the equilibrium constants $K_m^{\text{Substrate}}$ and K_m^{Nu} are expressed by referring these concentrations to the total volume of the observed rate constants, k_{obs} , based on Scheme 3 and on the above considerations, is given by the following equation:

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_2^w + \frac{k_2^m}{V} K_m^{\text{Substrate}} K_m^{\text{Nu}^-} [D_n]}{(1 + K_m^{\text{Substrate}} [D_n])(1 + K_m^{\text{Nu}^-} [D_n])} [\text{Nu}^-]_T \quad (2)$$

Second order rate constants at the micellar interface and binding constants of the hydroxamate ions to the cationic micelles were obtained by fitting eq. (2) to the experimental data and listed in Tables 3-5. In Figs. 4-7 the k_{obs} calculated values with this treatment are shown by solid lines.

The results depicted in Tables 3-5 let us to study the influence of the nature of the micelle for the reaction of phosphate esters with oximate and hydroxamate ion.

Fig. 6. Simulated rate-surfactant profile for the reaction of PNPB with NHA^- in CTAB micellar media (The solid lines are the results of fitting eq. (3)). Reaction condition: $[\text{PNPB}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Nu}^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{KCl}] = 0.1 \text{ M}$, $\text{pH} = 7.2$ (phosphate buffer), Temp. = 27°C , $\text{pH} = 9.2$ (borate buffer).

Fig. 7. Simulated rate-surfactant profile for the reaction of PNPDP with (■) AHA^- , (●) BHA^- in CTAB micellar media (The solid lines are the results of fitting (eq. 3)). Reaction condition: $[\text{PNPDPP}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Nu}^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{KCl}] = 0.1 \text{ M}$, $\text{pH} = 7.2$ (phosphate buffer), Temp. = 27°C , $\text{pH} = 9.2$ (borate buffer).

Fig. 4 shows pseudo-first order rate constant profile for the reaction of PNPB with NHA^- and BHA^- in CPB micellar media. It infers that k_{obs} value markedly increases, it attain maxima at cmc and then decrease. NHA^- show more reactivity compared to BHA^- in CPB micellar medium (Table 3). It is clear that surfactant enhance the rate of hydrolysis of PNPB till the cmc. The micellar binding constant of BHA^- , K_m^{BHA} , is relatively higher than, K_m^{NHA}

in CPB micellar medium. Larger micellar interaction of BHA⁻ provides greater micellar catalysis (k_2^m/k_2^w) of the factor 33 in CPB micellar medium, while 20 fold micellar catalysis was observed for NHA⁻. The significant acceleration of k_{obs} values have been observed for the reaction of BHA⁻ and AHA⁻ in CTAB, which may be due to the cooperative intrinsic nucleophilicity of BHA⁻ and AHA⁻ and micellar rate enhancements. Fig. 5 represents the pseudophase second order rate-surfactant profile for the reaction of PNPB with NHA⁻ in CTAB cationic micellar medium, it indicates the increase in surfactant concentration increases the k_{obs} value, marked increase in k_{obs} was observed till the cmc, then decrease in rate constant have been observed. Larger micellar binding constant have been observed for NHA⁻ and K_m^{NHA} in CPB micellar media compared to CTAB micellar medium, Tables 3-4 which is consistent with $k_2^m/k_2^w = 20$ and 3 respectively.

As shown in Fig. 6 hydrolysis of PNPDPDPP is catalyzed by the presence of CTAB. The k_{obs} values increases with increasing surfactant concentration, and reaches maximum at the cmc value and then decreases. The micellar binding constant in case of BHA⁻ (k_m^{BHA}) = 80.03

Table 3. Kinetic parameters obtained by applying pseudophase model for the nucleophilic reaction of PNPB in the presence of cationic micelles^a

Nu ⁻ k_2^w (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	CPB	
	K_m^{Nu} (M ⁻¹)	k_2^m (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
NHA ⁻ 1.9×10^{-1}	44.89 ± 16.88	(3.80 ± 0.8)
BHA ⁻ 9.6×10^{-2}	57.83 ± 13.48	(3.23 ± 0.4)

^aMicellar association constant of PNPB (K_m^{PNPB}) = 610 M⁻¹.

Table 4. Kinetic parameters obtained by applying pseudophase model for the nucleophilic reaction of PNPDPDPP in the presence of cationic micelles^a

Nu ⁻ k_2^w (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	CTAB	
	K_m^{Nu} (M ⁻¹)	k_2^m (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
NHA ⁻ 1.9×10^{-1}	24.78 ± 16.65	(5.7 ± 0.3) × 10 ⁻¹

Table 5. Kinetic parameters obtained by applying pseudophase model for the nucleophilic reaction of PNPDPDPP in the presence of cationic micelles^a

Nu ⁻ k_2^w (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	CTAB	
	K_m^{Nu} (M ⁻¹)	k_2^m (M ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
BHA ⁻ 8.6×10^{-3}	80.3 ± 14.21	(6.43 ± 0.06)
AHA ⁻ 5.8×10^{-2}	57.1 ± 20.9	(9.29 ± 0.04)

^aMicellar association constant of PNPDPDPP (K_m^{PNPDPP}) = 7000 M⁻¹.

is found to be higher as compared to AHA⁻ (k_m^{AHA}) = 56.06, larger micellar binding constant leads to larger rate enhancement (k_2^m/k_2^w) of the factor 747, while (k_2^m/k_2^w) = 160 fold catalysis (Table 4) was observed for AHA⁻.

Conclusions

The bimolecular reaction between PNPB and PNPDPDPP with different hydroxamate anions such as aceto-hydroxamate anion (AHA⁻), benzohydroxamate anion (BHA⁻) and naphthohydroxamate anion (NHA⁻) have been examined kinetically. In this study we found that the nucleophilic reactivities of hydroxamic acids are higher in the presence of cationic micellar media toward the PNPB and PNPDPDPP hydrolysis. The pH-dependent rate constants revealed that the hydrolytic reactions accelerated at the pH > pK_a. The enhanced reactivity beyond the pK_a of hydroxamic acid showed that the neutral hydroxamic acids are not active nucleophile. The k_{obs} value of the hydrolytic reactions increases linearly with increasing concentration of hydroxamate ions. The linear plots of k_{obs} vs nucleophile concentrations indicated that the hydroxamate ions are effective catalyst for hydrolysis of carboxylate and phosphate esters.

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